

SCORE-INFORMED IDENTIFICATION OF MISSING AND EXTRA NOTES IN PIANO RECORDINGS

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ABSTRACT

A main goal in music tuition is to enable a student to play a score without mistakes, where common mistakes include missing notes or playing additional extra ones. To automatically detect these mistakes, a first idea is to use a music transcription method to detect notes played in an audio recording and to compare the results with a corresponding score. However, as the number of transcription errors produced by standard methods is often considerably higher than the number of actual mistakes, the results are often of limited use. In contrast, our method exploits that the score already provides rough information about what we seek to detect in the audio, which allows us to construct a tailored transcription method. In particular, we employ score-informed source separation techniques to learn for each score pitch a set of templates capturing the spectral properties of that pitch. After extrapolating the resulting template dictionary to pitches not in the score, we estimate the activity of each MIDI pitch over time. Finally, making again use of the score, we choose for each pitch an individualized threshold to differentiate note onsets from spurious activity in an optimized way. We indicate the accuracy of our approach on a dataset of piano pieces commonly used in education.

1. INTRODUCTION

Automatic music transcription (AMT) has a long history in music signal processing, with early approaches dating back to the 1970s [1]. Despite the considerable interest in the topic, the challenges inherent to the task are still to overcome by state-of-the-art methods, with error rates for note detection typically between 20 and 40 percent, or even above, for polyphonic music [2–8]. While these error rates can drop considerably if rich prior knowledge can be provided [9, 10], the accuracy achievable in the more general case still prevents the use of AMT technologies in many useful applications.

This paper is motivated by a music tuition application,

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Figure 1. Given (a) an audio recording and (b) a score (e.g. as a MIDI file) for a piece of music, our method (c) estimates which notes have been played correctly (green/light crosses), have been missed (red/dark crosses for pitch 55) or have been added (blue/dark crosses for pitch 59) in the recording compared to the score.

where a central learning outcome is to enable the student to read and reproduce (simple) musical scores using an instrument. In this scenario, a natural use of AMT technologies could be to detect which notes have been played by the student and to compare the results against a reference score – this way one could give feedback, highlighting where notes in the score have not been played (*missed notes*) and where notes have been played that cannot be found in the score

(*extra notes*). Unfortunately, the relatively low accuracy of standard AMT methods prevents such applications: the number of mistakes a student makes is typically several times lower than the errors produced by AMT methods.

Using a standard AMT method in a music tuition scenario as described above, however, would ignore a highly valuable source of prior knowledge: the score. Therefore, the authors in [11] make use of the score by first aligning the score to the audio, synthesizing the score using a wavetable method, and then transcribing both the real and the synthesized audio using an AMT method. To lower the number of falsely detected notes for the real recording, the method discards any detected note if the same note is also detected in the synthesized recording while no corresponding note can be found in the score. Here, the underlying assumption is that in such a situation, the local note constellation might lead to uncertainty in the spectrum, which could cause an error in their proposed method. To improve the results further, the method requires the availability of single note recordings for the instrument to be transcribed (under the same recording conditions) – a requirement not unrealistic to fulfil in this application scenario but leading to additional demands for the user. Under these additional constraints, the method lowered the number of transcription errors considerably compared to standard AMT methods. To the best of the authors’ knowledge, the method presented in [11] is the only score-informed transcription method in existence.

Overall, the core concept in [11] is to use the score information to post-process the transcription results from a standard AMT method. In contrast, the main idea in this paper is to exploit the available score information to adapt the transcription method itself to a given recording. To this end, we use the score to modify two central components of an AMT system: the set of spectral patterns used to identify note objects in a time-frequency representation, and the decision process responsible for differentiating actual note events from spurious note activities. In particular, after aligning the score to the audio recording, we employ the score information to constrain the learning process in non-negative matrix factorization similar to strategies used in score-informed source separation [12]. As a result, we obtain for each pitch in the score a set of template vectors that capture the spectro-temporal behaviour of that pitch – adapted to the given recording. Next, we extrapolate the template vectors to cover the entire MIDI range (including pitches not used in the score), and compute an activity for each pitch over time. After that we again make use of the score to analyze the resulting activities: we set, for each pitch, a threshold used to differentiate between noise and real notes such that the resulting note onsets correspond to the given score as closely as possible. Finally, the resulting transcription is compared to the given score, which enables the classification of note events as correct, missing or extra. This way, our method can use highly adapted spectral patterns in the acoustic model eliminating the need for additional single note recordings, and remove many spurious errors in the detection stage. An example output of our method is shown in Fig. 1, where correctly played notes

are marked in green, missing notes in red and extra notes in blue.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we describe the details of our proposed method. In Section 3, we report on experimental results using a dataset comprising recordings of pieces used in piano education. We conclude in Section 4 with a prospect on future work.

2. PROPOSED METHOD

2.1 Step 1: Score-Audio Alignment

As a first step in our proposed method, we align a score (given as a MIDI file) to an audio recording of a student playing the corresponding piece. For this purpose, we employ the method proposed in [13], which combines chroma with onset indicator features to increase the temporal accuracy of the resulting alignments. Since we expect differences on the note level between the score and the audio recording related to the playing mistakes, we manually checked the temporal accuracy of the method but found the alignments to be robust in this scenario. It should be noted, however, that the method is not designed to cope with structural differences (e.g. the student adding repetitions of some segments in the score, or leaving out certain parts) – if such differences are to be expected, partial alignment techniques should be used instead [14, 15].

2.2 Step 2: Score-Informed Adaptive Dictionary Learning

As a result of the alignment, we now roughly know for each note in the score, the corresponding or expected position in the audio. Next, we use this information to learn how each pitch manifests in a time-frequency representation of the audio recording, employing techniques similarly used in score-informed source separation (SISS). There are various SISS approaches to choose from: Early methods essentially integrated the score information into existing signal models, which already drastically boosted the stability of the methods. These signal models, however, were designed for blind source separation and thus have the trade-off between the capacity to model details (*variance*) and the robustness in the parameter estimation (*bias*) heavily leaned towards the bias. For example, various approaches make specific assumptions to keep the parameter space small, such as that partials of a harmonic sound behave like a Gaussian in frequency direction [16], are highly stationary in a single frame [17] or occur as part of predefined clusters of harmonics [6]. However, with score information providing extremely rich prior knowledge, later approaches found that the variance-bias trade-off can be shifted considerably towards variance.

For our method, we adapt an approach that makes fewer assumptions about how partials manifests and rather learns these properties from data. The basic idea is to constrain a (shift-invariant) non-negative matrix factorization (NMF) based model using the score, making only use of rough information and allowing the learning process to identify

Figure 2. Score-Informed Dictionary Learning: Using multiplicative updates in non-negative matrix factorization, semantically meaningful constraints can easily be enforced by setting individual entries to zero (dark blue): Templates and activations after the initialization (a)/(b) and after the optimization process (c)/(d).

the details, see also [12]. Since we focus on piano recordings where tuning shifts in a single recording or vibrato do not occur, we do not make use of shift invariance. In the following, we assume general familiarity with NMF and refer to [18] for further details. Let $V \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times N}$ be a magnitude spectrogram of our audio recording, with logarithmic spacing for the frequency axis. We approximate V as a product of two non-negative matrices $W \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times K}$ and $H \in \mathbb{R}^{K \times N}$, where the columns of W are called (spectral) templates and the rows in H the corresponding activities. We start by allocating two NMF templates to each pitch in the score – one for the attack and one for the sustain part. The sustain part of a piano is harmonic in nature and thus we do not expect significant energy in frequencies that lie between its partials. We implement this constraint as in [12] by initializing for each sustain template only those entries with positive values that are close to a harmonic of the pitch associated with the template, i.e. entries between partials are set to zero, compare Fig. 2a. This constraint will remain intact throughout the NMF learning process as we will use multiplicative update rules and thus setting entries to zero is a straightforward way to efficiently implement certain constraints in NMF, while letting some room for the NMF process to learn where exactly each partial is and how it spectrally manifests. The attack templates are initialized with a uniform energy distribution to account for their broadband properties.

Constraints on the activations are implemented in a similar way: activations are set to zero if a pitch is known to be inactive in a time segment, with a tolerance used to

account for alignment inaccuracies, compare Fig. 2b. To counter the lack of constraints for attack templates, the corresponding activations are subject to stricter rules: attack templates are only allowed to be used in a close vicinity around expected onset positions. After these initializations, the method presented in [12] employs the commonly used Lee-Seung NMF update rules [18] to minimize a generalized Kullback-Leibler divergence between V and WH . This way, the NMF learning process refines the information within the unconstrained areas on W and H .

However, we propose a modified learning process that enhances the broadband properties for the attack templates. More precisely, we include attack templates to bind the broadband energy related to onsets and thus reduce the number of spurious note detections. We observed, however, that depending on the piece, the attack templates would capture too much of the harmonic energy, which interfered with the note detection later on. Since harmonic energy manifest as peaks along the frequency axis, we discourage such peaks for attack templates and favour smoothness using an additional spectral continuity constraint in the objective function:

$$f(W, H) := \sum_{m,n} V_{m,n} \log\left(\frac{V_{m,n}}{(WH)_{m,n}}\right) - V_{m,n} + (WH)_{m,n} + \sigma \sum_m \sum_{k \in \mathcal{A}} (W_{m,k} - W_{m-1,k})^2$$

where the first sum is the generalized Kullback-Leibler divergence and the second sum is a total variation term in frequency direction, with $\mathcal{A} \subset \{1, \dots, K\}$ denoting the index set of attack templates and σ controlling the relative importance of the two terms. Note that $W_{m,k} - W_{m-1,k} = (F \star W_{:,k})(m)$, where $W_{:,k}$ denotes the k -th column of W and $F = (-1, 1)$ is a high-pass filter. To find a local minimum for this bi-convex problem, we propose the following iterative update rules alternating between W and H (we omit the derivation for a lack of space but followed similar strategies as used for example in [19]):

$$W_{m,k} \leftarrow W_{m,k} \cdot \frac{\sum_n H_{k,n} \frac{V_{m,n}}{(WH)_{m,n}} + \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(k) 2\sigma(W_{m+1,k} + W_{m-1,k})}{\sum_n H_{k,n} + \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(k) 4\sigma W_{m,k}}$$

$$W_{m,k} \leftarrow \frac{W_{m,k}}{\sum_{\tilde{m}} W_{\tilde{m},k}}$$

$$H_{k,n} \leftarrow H_{k,n} \cdot \frac{\sum_m W_{m,k} \frac{V_{m,n}}{(WH)_{m,n}}}{\sum_m W_{m,k}}$$

where $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}$ is the indicator function for \mathcal{A} . The result of this update process is shown in Fig. 2c and d. It is clearly visible how the learning process refined the unconstrained areas in W and H , closely reflecting the acoustical properties in the recording. Further, the total variation term led to attack templates with broadband characteristics for all pitches, while still capturing the non-uniform, pitch dependent energy distribution typical for piano attacks.

2.3 Step 3: Dictionary Extrapolation and Residual Modelling

All notes not reflected by the score naturally lead to a difference or residual between V and WH as observed also in [20]. To model this residual, the next step in our proposed method is to extrapolate our learnt dictionary of spectral templates to the complete MIDI range, which enables us to transcribe pitches not used in the score. Since we use a time-frequency representation with a logarithmic frequency scale, we can implement this step by a simple shift operation: for each MIDI pitch not in the score, we find the closest pitch in the score and shift the two associated templates by the number of frequency bins corresponding to the difference between the two pitches. After this operation we can use our recording-specific full-range dictionary to compute activities for all MIDI pitches. To this end, we add an activity row to H for each extrapolated template and reset any zero constraints in H by adding a small value to all entries. Then, without updating W , we re-estimate this full-range H using the same update rules as given above.

2.4 Step 4: Onset Detection Using Score-Informed Adaptive Thresholding

After convergence, we next analyze H to detect note onsets. A straightforward solution would be to add, for each pitch and in each time frame, the activity for the two templates associated with that pitch and detecting peaks afterwards in time direction. This approach, however, leads to several problems. To illustrate these, we look again at Fig. 2c, and compare the different attack templates learnt by our procedure. As we can see, the individual attack templates do differ for different pitches, yet their energy distribution is quite broadband leading to considerable overlap or similarity between some attack templates. Therefore, when we compute H there is often very little difference with respect to the objective function if we activate the attack template associated with the correct pitch, or an attack template for a neighboring pitch (from an optimization point of view, these similarities lead to relatively wide plateaus in the objective function, where all solutions are almost equally good). The activity in these neighboring pitches led to wrong note detections.

As one solution, inspired by the methods presented in [21, 22], we initially incorporated a Markov process into the learning process described above. Such a process can be employed to model that if a certain template (e.g. for the attack part) is being used in one frame, another template (e.g. for the sustain part) has to be used in the next frame. This extension often solved the problem described above as attack templates cannot be used without their sustain parts anymore. Unfortunately, the dictionary learning process with this extension is not (bi-)convex anymore and in practice we found the learning process to regularly get stuck in poor local minima leading to less accurate transcription results.

A much simpler solution, however, solved the above problems in our experiments similar to the Markov process, without the numerical issues associated with it: we sim-

ply ignore activities for attack templates. Here, the idea is that as long as the broadband onset energy is meaningfully captured by some templates, we do not need to care about spurious note detections caused by this energy and can focus entirely on detecting peaks in the cleaner, more discriminative sustain part to detect the notes (compare also Fig. 2d). Since this simpler solution turned out to be more robust, efficient and accurate overall, we use this approach in the following. The result of using only the sustain activities is shown in the background of Fig. 1. Comparing these results to standard NMF-based transcription methods, these activities are much cleaner and easier to interpret – a result of using learnt, recording-specific templates.

As a next step, we need to differentiate real onsets from spurious activity. A common technique in the AMT literature is to simply use a global threshold to identify peaks in the activity. As another approach often used for sustained instruments like the violin or the flute, hidden Markov models (HMMs) implement a similar idea but add capabilities to smooth over local activity fluctuations, which might otherwise be detected as onsets [2]. We tried both approaches for our method but given the distinctive, fast energy decay for piano notes, we could not identify significant benefits for the somewhat more complex HMM solution and thus only report on our thresholding based results. A main difference in our approach to standard AMT methods, however, is the use of *pitch-dependent* thresholds, which we optimize again using the score information. The main reason why this pitch dependency is useful is that loudness perception in the human auditory system non-linearly depends on the frequency and is highly complex for non-sinusoidal sounds. Therefore, to reach a specific loudness for a given pitch, a pianist might strike the corresponding key with different intensity compared to another pitch, which can lead to considerable differences in measured energy.

To find pitch-wise thresholds, our method first generates $C \in \mathbb{N}$ threshold candidates, which are uniformly distributed between 0 and $\max_{k,n} H_{k,n}$. Next, we use each candidate to find note onsets in each activity row in H that is associated with a pitch in the score. Then, we evaluate how many of the detected onsets correspond to notes in the aligned score, how many are extra and how many are missing – expressed as a precision, recall and F-measure value for each candidate and pitch. To increase the robustness of this step, in particular for pitches with only few notes, we compute these candidate ratings not only using the notes for a single pitch but include the notes and onsets for the N closest neighbouring pitches. For example, to rate threshold candidates for MIDI pitch P , we compute the F-measure using all onsets and notes corresponding to, for example, MIDI pitch $P - 1$ to $P + 1$. The result of this step is a curve for each pitch showing the F-measure for each candidate, from which we choose the lowest threshold maximizing the F-measure, compare Fig. 3. This way, we can choose a threshold that generates the least amount of extra and missing notes, or alternatively, a threshold that maximizes the match between the detected onsets and the given score. Thresholds for pitches not used in the score are

Figure 3. Adaptive and pitch-dependent thresholding: For each pitch we choose the smallest threshold maximizing the F-measure we obtain by comparing the detected offsets against the aligned nominal score. The red entries show threshold candidates having maximal F-measure.

interpolated from the thresholds for neighbouring pitches that are in the score.

2.5 Step 5: Score-Informed Onset Classification

Using these thresholds, we create a final transcription result for each pitch. As our last step, we try to identify for each detected onset a corresponding note in the aligned score, which allows us to classify each onset as either *correct* (i.e. note is played and is in the score) or *extra* (i.e. played but not in the score). All score notes without a corresponding onset are classified as *missing*. To identify these correspondences we use a temporal tolerance T of ± 250 ms, where T is a parameter that can be increased to account for local alignment problems or if the student cannot yet follow the rhythm faithfully (e.g. we observed concurrent notes being pulled apart by students for non-musical reasons). This classification is indicated in Fig. 1 using crosses having different colours for each class.

3. EXPERIMENTS

3.1 Dataset

We indicate the performance of our proposed method using a dataset¹ originally compiled in [11]. The dataset comprises seven pieces shown in Table 1 that were taken from the syllabus used by the Associated Board of the Royal Schools of Music for grades 1 and 2 in the 2011/2012 period. Making various intentional mistakes, a pianist played these pieces on a Yamaha U3 Disklavier, an acoustic upright piano capable of returning MIDI events encoding the keys being pressed. The dataset includes for each piece an audio recording, a MIDI file encoding the reference score, as well as three annotation MIDI files encoding the extra, missing and correctly played notes, respectively.

In initial tests using this dataset, we observed that the annotations were created in a quite rigid way. In particular, several note events in the score were associated with one missing and one extra note, which were in close vicinity of each other. Listening to the corresponding audio recording, we found that these events were seemingly played correctly. This could indicate that the annotation process was potentially a bit too strict in terms of temporal tolerance. Therefore, we modified the three annotation files in some cases. Other corrections included the case that a single

ID	Composer	Title
1	Josef Haydn	Symp. No. 94: Andante (Hob I:94-02)
2	James Hook	Gavotta (Op. 81 No. 3)
3	Pauline Hall	Tarantella
4	Felix Swinestead	A Tender Flower
5	Johann Krieger	Sechs musicalische Partien: Bourrée
6	Johannes Brahms	The Sandman (WoO 31 No. 4)
7	Tim Richards (arr.)	Down by the Riverside

Table 1. Pieces of music used in the evaluation, see also [11].

score note was played more than once and we re-assigned in some cases which of the repeated notes should be considered as extra notes and which as the correctly played note, taking the timing of other notes into account. Further, some notes in the score were not played but were not found in the corresponding annotation of missing notes. We make these slightly modified annotation files available online². It should be noted that these modifications were made before we started evaluating our proposed method.

3.2 Metrics

Our method yields a transcription along with a classification into correct, extra and missing notes. Using the available ground truth annotations, we can evaluate each class individually. In each class, we can identify up to a small temporal tolerance the number of true positives (TP), false positives (FP) and false negatives (FN). From these, we can derive the *Precision* $P = \frac{TP}{TP+FP}$, the *Recall* $R = \frac{TP}{TP+FN}$, the *F-measure* $2PR/(P+R)$ and the *Accuracy* $A = \frac{TP}{TP+FP+FN}$. We use a temporal tolerance of ± 250 ms to account for the inherent difficulties aligning different versions of a piece with local differences, i.e. playing errors can lead to local uncertainties which position in the one version corresponds to which position in the other.

3.3 Results

The results for our method are shown in Table 2 for each class and piece separately. As we can see for the ‘correct’ class, with an F-measure of more than 99% the results are beyond the limits of standard transcription methods. However, this is expected as we can use prior knowledge provided by the score to tune our method to detect exactly these events. More interestingly are the results for the events we do not expect. With an F-measure of 94.5%, the results for the ‘missing’ class are almost on the same level as for the ‘correct’ class. The F-measure for the ‘extra’ class is 77.2%, which would be a good result for a standard AMT method but it is well below the results for the other two classes.

Let us investigate the reasons. A good starting point is piece number 6 where the results for the ‘extra’ class are well below average. In this recording, MIDI notes in the score with a pitch of 54 and 66 are consistently replaced in the recording with notes of MIDI pitch 53 and 65. In particular, pitches 54 and 66 are never actually played in the recording. Therefore, the dictionary learning process

¹ available online: <http://c4dm.eecs.qmul.ac.uk/rdr/>

² <http://www.eecs.qmul.ac.uk/~ewerts/>

ID	Class	Prec.	Recall	F-Meas.	Accur.
1	C	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
	E	100.0	71.4	83.3	71.4
	M	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
2	C	100.0	99.7	99.8	99.7
	E	90.0	81.8	85.7	75.0
	M	92.3	100.0	96.0	92.3
3	C	99.2	99.2	99.2	98.4
	E	100.0	66.7	80.0	66.7
	M	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
4	C	98.7	100.0	99.3	98.7
	E	80.0	80.0	80.0	66.7
	M	100.0	85.7	92.3	85.7
5	C	99.5	98.6	99.1	98.1
	E	75.0	92.3	82.8	70.6
	M	87.5	100.0	93.3	87.5
6	C	99.2	99.2	99.2	98.4
	E	50.0	52.9	51.4	34.6
	M	93.3	93.3	93.3	87.5
7	C	99.5	97.1	98.3	96.7
	E	75.0	80.0	77.4	63.2
	M	76.2	100.0	86.5	76.2
Avg.	C	99.4	99.1	99.3	98.6
	E	81.4	75.0	77.2	64.0
	M	92.8	97.0	94.5	89.9

Table 2. Evaluation results for our proposed method in percent.

Figure 4. Cause of errors in piece 6: Activation matrix with ground truth annotations showing the position of notes in the ‘correct’, ‘extra’ and ‘missing’ classes.

in step 2 cannot observe how these two pitches manifest in the recording and thus cannot learn a meaningful template. Yet, being in a direct neighbourhood, the dictionary extrapolation in step 3 will use the learnt templates for pitch 54 and 66 to derive templates for pitches 53 and 65. Thus, these templates, despite the harmonicity constraints which still lead to some enforced structure in the templates, do not well represent how pitches 53 and 65 actually manifest in the recording and thus the corresponding activations will typically be low. As a result the extra notes were not detected as such by our method. We illustrate these effects in Fig. 4, where a part of the final full-range activation matrix is shown in the background and the corresponding ground-truth annotations are plotted on top as coloured circles. It is clearly visible, that the activations for pitch 53 are well below the level for the other notes. Excluding piece 6 from the evaluation, we obtain an average F-measure of 82% for ‘extra’ notes.

Finally, we reproduce the evaluation results reported for

Class	C	E	M
Accuracy	93.2	60.5	49.2

Table 3. Results reported for the method proposed in [11]. Remark: Values are not directly comparable with the results shown in Table 2 due to using different ground truth annotations in the evaluation.

the method proposed in [11] in Table 3. It should be noted, however, that the results are not directly comparable with the results in Table 2 as we modified the underlying ground truth annotations. However, some general observations might be possible. In particular, since the class of ‘correct’ notes is the biggest in numbers, the results for this class are roughly comparable. In terms of accuracy, the number of errors in this class is five times higher in [11] (6.8 errors vs 1.4 errors per 100 notes). In this context, we want to remark that the method presented in [11] relied on the availability of recordings of single notes for the instrument in use, in contrast to ours. The underlying reason for the difference in accuracy between the two methods could be that instead of post-processing a standard AMT method, our approach yields a transcription method optimized in each step using score information. This involves a different signal model using several templates with dedicated meaning per pitch, the use of score information to optimize the onset detection and the use of pitch-dependent detection thresholds. Since the number of notes in the ‘extra’ and ‘missing’ classes are lower, it might not be valid to draw conclusions here.

4. CONCLUSIONS

We presented a novel method for detecting deviations from a given score in the form of missing and extra notes in corresponding audio recordings. In contrast to previous methods, our approach employs the information provided by the score to adapt the transcription process from the start, yielding a method specialized in transcribing a specific recording and corresponding piece. Our method is inspired by techniques commonly used in score-informed source separation that learn a highly optimized dictionary of spectral templates to model the given recording. Our evaluation results showed a high F-measure for notes in the classes ‘correct’ and ‘missing’, and a good F-measure for the ‘extra’ class. Our error analysis for the latter indicated possible directions for improvements, in particular for the dictionary extrapolation step. Further it would be highly valuable to create new datasets to better understand the behaviour of score-informed transcription methods under more varying recording conditions and numbers of mistakes made.

Acknowledgements: This work was partly funded by EP-SRC grant EP/L019981/1. The International Audio Laboratories Erlangen are a joint institution of the Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg (FAU) and Fraunhofer Institut für Integrierte Schaltungen IIS. Sandler acknowledges the support of the Royal Society as a recipient of a Wolfson Research Merit Award.

5. REFERENCES

- [1] James A Moorer. On the transcription of musical sound by computer. *Computer Music Journal*, pages 32–38, 1977.
- [2] Anssi P. Klapuri and Manuel Davy, editors. *Signal Processing Methods for Music Transcription*. Springer, New York, 2006.
- [3] Masataka Goto. A real-time music-scene-description system: Predominant-F0 estimation for detecting melody and bass lines in real-world audio signals. *Speech Communication (ISCA Journal)*, 43(4):311–329, 2004.
- [4] Graham E. Poliner and Daniel P.W. Ellis. A discriminative model for polyphonic piano transcription. *EURASIP Journal on Advances in Signal Processing*, 2007(1), 2007.
- [5] Zhiyao Duan, Bryan Pardo, and Changshui Zhang. Multiple fundamental frequency estimation by modeling spectral peaks and non-peak regions. *IEEE Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing*, 18(8):2121–2133, 2010.
- [6] Emmanuel Vincent, Nancy Bertin, and Roland Badeau. Adaptive harmonic spectral decomposition for multiple pitch estimation. *IEEE Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing*, 18(3):528–537, 2010.
- [7] Sebastian Böck and Markus Schedl. Polyphonic piano note transcription with recurrent neural networks. In *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, pages 121–124, Kyoto, Japan, 2012.
- [8] Siddharth Sigtia, Emmanouil Benetos, and Simon Dixon. An end-to-end neural network for polyphonic piano music transcription. *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing*, PP(99):1–1, 2016.
- [9] Holger Kirchhoff, Simon Dixon, and Anssi Klapuri. Multi-template shift-variant non-negative matrix deconvolution for semi-automatic music transcription. In *Proceedings of the International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference (ISMIR)*, pages 415–420, 2012.
- [10] Sebastian Ewert and Mark Sandler. Piano transcription in the studio using an extensible alternating directions framework. *(to appear)*, 2016.
- [11] Emmanouil Benetos, Anssi Klapuri, and Simon Dixon. Score-informed transcription for automatic piano tutoring. In *Proceedings of the European Signal Processing Conference (EUSIPCO)*, pages 2153–2157, 2012.
- [12] Sebastian Ewert, Bryan Pardo, Meinard Müller, and Mark D. Plumbley. Score-informed source separation for musical audio recordings: An overview. *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine*, 31(3):116–124, May 2014.
- [13] Sebastian Ewert, Meinard Müller, and Peter Grosche. High resolution audio synchronization using chroma onset features. In *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, pages 1869–1872, Taipei, Taiwan, 2009.
- [14] Andreas Arzt, Sebastian Böck, Sebastian Flossmann, Harald Frostel, Martin Gasser, and Gerhard Widmer. The complete classical music companion v0.9. In *Proceedings of the AES International Conference on Semantic Audio*, pages 133–137, London, UK, 18–20 2014.
- [15] Meinard Müller and Daniel Appelt. Path-constrained partial music synchronization. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, pages 65–68, Las Vegas, Nevada, USA, 2008.
- [16] Katsutoshi Itoyama, Masataka Goto, Kazunori Komatani, Tetsuya Ogata, and Hiroshi G. Okuno. Instrument equalizer for query-by-example retrieval: Improving sound source separation based on integrated harmonic and inharmonic models. In *Proceedings of the International Conference for Music Information Retrieval (ISMIR)*, pages 133–138, Philadelphia, USA, 2008.
- [17] Romain Hennequin, Bertrand David, and Roland Badeau. Score informed audio source separation using a parametric model of non-negative spectrogram. In *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, pages 45–48, Prague, Czech Republic, 2011.
- [18] Daniel D. Lee and H. Sebastian Seung. Algorithms for non-negative matrix factorization. In *Proceedings of the Neural Information Processing Systems (NIPS)*, pages 556–562, Denver, CO, USA, 2000.
- [19] Andrzej Cichocki, Rafal Zdunek, and Anh Huy Phan. *Nonnegative Matrix and Tensor Factorizations: Applications to Exploratory Multi-Way Data Analysis and Blind Source Separation*. John Wiley and Sons, 2009.
- [20] Jonathan Driedger, Harald Grohgan, Thomas Prätzlich, Sebastian Ewert, and Meinard Müller. Score-informed audio decomposition and applications. In *Proceedings of the ACM International Conference on Multimedia (ACM-MM)*, pages 541–544, Barcelona, Spain, 2013.
- [21] Emmanouil Benetos and Simon Dixon. Multiple-instrument polyphonic music transcription using a temporally constrained shift-invariant model. *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 133(3):1727–1741, 2013.
- [22] Sebastian Ewert, Mark D. Plumbley, and Mark Sandler. A dynamic programming variant of non-negative matrix deconvolution for the transcription of struck string instruments. In *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, pages 569–573, Brisbane, Australia, 2015.